

Impact of Service Quality, Customer Relationship Management and Perceived Value on Brand Loyalty with Mediation Role of Customer Satisfaction

Author's Details:

Rehana Kosar^{1*} Shifa Rthore² Komel Jamil³ Maria Ghani⁴

^{1,2,3} Student, Department of management Sciences, Riphah international University Rawalpindi Pakistan
⁴ (PhD scholar), Southwest Jiaotong University China

Correspondence Author: Rehanakousar21@gmail.com - Department of management Science, Riphah International University Rawalpindi Pakistan.

Abstract

Customer satisfaction is one of the key objectives of service organizations because satisfaction leads the customers to be loyal and loyalty can be the source of competitive edge for the organization. Therefore, this study is designed to investigate the mediating role of customer satisfaction between service quality, CRM, perceived value, and brand loyalty in the overall service sectors of Pakistan. For this study, the targeted population consists of the different consumers who were involved in consuming services of both public and private sectors. We chose the "convenient sampling technique". Among 302 respondents result from only 215 (71%) results were used through quantitative research methodology. The results indicate that service quality, customer relationship management, and perceived value are the key drivers in enhancing brand loyalty when customer satisfaction is mediated in their relationship. For analysis, the collection was generated through SPSS. The findings confirm highly positive correspondence among variables considers for this study.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Relationship Management, Perceived Value, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Loyalty.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of "Brand Loyalty" has gained ample interest in both marketing practitioners and academic researchers over the recent period (Worthington et al., 2009). Brand loyalty is a complicated phenomenon comprised of behavioral and attitudinal elements. In the field of research brand loyalty have a strong history. It might be considered as a "Superior case of affiliation marketing" somewhere the customer has a deep inner attachment to the consumer brand (Jacoby et al., 1973; Fournier, 198). In the marketing literature, the significance of brand loyalty has been recognized for the past three decades (Howard & Sheth, 1969). In a service organization brand loyalty is the most important construct that leads to repurchase by customers. Though, loyal customers indulge in repurchase as the basic principle in the competitive market. Brand strategy is the company's most important tool as it enables the customer to understand the product and/or services they offer (Kim et al, 2008). Many organizations have recognized the brand loyalty program as part of their relationship development activates. Brand loyalty is a complex concept. In the service sector, it is defined as a broad type of observed behavior (Bloemer et al.1999).

In today's highly competitive environment, industrial organizations are competing based on their services. In the 1980s access to services was considered a luxury. In this modern era, lifestyle is changing which contributes to world growth. To reinvent the public sector from the time when the 1990s service quality and customer satisfaction have been a central strategic criterion. Service quality is one of the most essential elements in determining the expected and perceived service outcome of a business customer. Whether it is manufacturing, service, or quality services the excellence of business and business services paramount importance (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1982), (Lewis &Booms, 1983), (Parasuraman et al, 1985). The service sector shows a fundamental role in the economies of many countries and becomes more important day by day. Now a day's in a worldwide competitive situation high superiority service is well thought-out as a successive approach and for continued existence (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Reichheld & Sasser, 1990; Zeithaml et al., 1990).

It is important to understand that gaining customers and building loyalty takes time. In the past research has repeatedly shown that the service quality influences the organization's results, such as B. superior.....? (Poretla & Thanassoulis, 2005).

The earlier investigation gave focused on CRM's strategy elements, such as the correlation between satisfaction of the customer and corporate performance (Kamakura et al., 2002), relation among profitability and buyer loyalty (Kamakura et al; 2002), heterogeneity of customer productivity (Reinartz & Kumar 2000), and Customer loyalty program (Niraj, 2000). In the present computerized world, the headway of innovation offers extraordinary advantages to shoppers. Buyers then again become increasingly needy to the use of innovation in everyday exercises particularly in the service industry, for example, the same time usage of services. Huge difficulties face by advertisers especially keeping shoppers' brand devotion to their item (Luarn & Lin, 2003; Nasir, 2005) from separated advertising exertion expanding brand loyalty is to convey more prominent worth. Worth is basic in satisfying purchasers' needs and needs.

Brand loyalty has been referred to as one of the greatest obstacles for service organizations and researchers have emphasized a lot on unveiling the determinants of brand loyalty. The service organization needs to cognize all the factors affecting service organization brand loyalty so that effective and efficient strategies could be developed to communicate their message to the target market. As a predecessor study of brand loyalty is very limited. To affiliation this hole, this assessment starts this progression to decide brand loyalty through covering all industrial zones of Pakistan in a particular assessment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service quality and customer satisfaction

As indicated by Lewis and Booms (1983), service quality is a size of the extent to which the services supplied meet buyer expectations. Providing quality service means consistently meeting customer expectations. In an in-depth study of the quality of services performed by examiners, it was believed that the quality of services can be estimated using the SERVQUAL tool (Parasuraman et al., 1988, 1991b, 1994). And managed as expected - the presentation gap model (Zeithaml et al., 1988; Zeithaml & Bitner, 1996). In addition, Chou and Kim (2009) create that service quality has a progressive influence on customer satisfaction. As the research of Imtiyaz and Ilyas (2018) analyzed the interconnecting relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction.

H₁: There is significances positive connection between SQ and CS.

Customer Relationship Management and Customer Satisfaction

According, Piccoli, and Applegate (2003) describe in what way Wyndham uses IT implements to provide a customer with a regular service involvement for their different properties. Improved personalization capacity and reduced unpredictability of the consumer capability improve the perceived quality, which in the sequence has an emotional impression on customer satisfaction. Customer relationship management applications similarly support companies to manage customer relationships more efficiently in all phases of initiating, maintaining, and ending relationships (Reinartz, Krafft, & Hoyer 2004). According to the study of Kolis and Jirinova (2013) due to the positive impact of CRM on Customer satisfaction company's financial position has become strong.

H₂: CRM has significance and positive association with CS.

Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction

Perceived value is repeatedly foreseen to contain a buyer's judgment of the part of perceived paybacks to perceived payments (Wang et al., 2012). As per (Zeitham, 1988), perceived value is the customer's generally speaking estimate of the function of an element dependent on the observation of what is acquired and what is given. Consumer's impression of important worth is affected by compares in monetary expenses, non-financial expenses, customer's flavors, and customer's qualities (Bolton & Drew, 1991). Although the finding of Kusumawati and Rahayu, (2020) proved that perceived value and customer satisfaction are interconnected.

H₃: PV has significance and positive association with CS.

Mediation of CS between SQ and BL

(Bloemer et al. 1998) utilized a model to demonstrate in what way the emotional picture, service quality, and customer satisfaction impact brand loyalty. The aftereffects of this exploration indicate that the psychological image impacts loyalty indirectly and concluded the worth of the service. Then again, service quality impacts loyalty directly and indirectly (done satisfaction). Furthermore, this exploration has shown that trustworthiness and market situation is comparatively key incentives for loyalty to services provided by industrial companies.

Ahmed (2011) proposes that satisfaction can be decided by the association concerning service quality and brand loyalty. Ghafoor and Asad-ur-Rehman (2014) show that there is a helpful association between customer satisfaction and brand loyalty. They additionally recommended that branding can be accomplished by expanding consumer loyalty and giving high brand value.

H₄: CS is absolutely mediating in the connection of SQ and BL.

Mediation of CS between CRM and BL

According to Roy and Shekhar (2010), the introduction of effective customer-oriented strategies to create, develop, improve, and maintain customer relationships is crucial to achieving a lasting competitive advantage in the market. Yueh et al. (2010) suggest that companies can use customer relationship management to interact successfully with their customers in a dynamic and profitable manner. In this context, it becomes clear what role customer relationship management plays for the organization to improve the competitive advantage of the business. Dowling (2002) suggests that the customer relationship management system should improve customer response, customer satisfaction, and brand loyalty.

H₅: CS is positively facilitating amongst CRM and BL.

Mediation of CS between PV and BL

An examination by Yang and Peterson (2004) on customer Perceived Value, Customer Satisfaction, and loyalty uses Consumer Satisfaction as an intermediary between Perceived Value and loyalty and shows that Customer Satisfaction has an optimistic and important influence on the connection between perceived value and loyalty. They additionally recommended that associations that make progress toward loyalty should concentrate on consumer satisfaction. They also advocated that organizations that strive for loyalty have to attend to customer satisfaction. From one perspective, they depict that brand loyalty, satisfaction, and Perceived Value are just significant if consumer loyalty lives up to their desires or is better than expected. Different specialists who use Customer Satisfaction as a mediating among Perceived Value and loyalty are (Yang & Peterson 2004); (Ishaq 2012); (Hussain 2016).

H₆: CS is clearly mediating in the connection of PV and BL.

Customer satisfaction and brand loyalty

Satisfaction and loyalty are linked, but different from each other (Ball et al., 2004). Fulfillment is one of the greatest significant harbingers of loyalty that has been mentioned in different examinations (Forouzandeh & Ahmadi, 2010). As per Heskett et al. (1997), just 100% of delighted consumers are faithful to the brand and consume comparatively high buyback charges. Bowen and Chen (2001) also found that clients must be enormously delighted with their brand loyalty. A finding of Studied on MacDonald's Maroc has been shown that quality of food, quality of staff itself providing a pleasurable smooth intake related satisfaction and more satisfied customer are more loyal with the brand (Raduzzi & Massey 2019).

H₇: CS has a significant optimistic connection with BL.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To discover the effect of SQ on CS.
- To discover the effect of CRM on CS.

- To discover the effect of PV on CS.
- To prove the mediating effect of CS among SQ, CRM, PV, and BL.
- To discover the effect of CS on BL.

COCEPTUAL FRAMWORK

METHODOLOGY

The recent research is a quantitative investigation in which influence of service quality; perceive value and customer relationship management on brand loyalty. Moreover, instantaneous research also explored the role of customer satisfaction as a mediator on brand loyalty. The methodology used in this study is quantitative research methodology. Feedback was conducted from the targeted population through an adapted questionnaire. All the respondents were briefly and personally instruct before administering the questionnaires also if they were any queries were addressed before that. The research was based on self-reported observation of the target population concerning all variables.

The targeted population for current research comprised of the different customers who were involved in consuming services of the public and private sectors. The key reason for this type of sampling is to choose a respective group of elements that are comprised of required characteristics. Five points Likert scale questioner was used, weights were given to all responses from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For analysis, Demographic frequencies were calculated. The regression analysis, and correlation analysis, were generated using SPSS. Using descriptive statistics, factor and correlation, regression analysis all the Hypotheses were tested. The correlation was used to investigate the relation amongst variables. While regression analysis was used to examine the percentage change caused by independent variables into dependent variables also Cronbach Alpha test was used to check internal reliability. Moreover, respondent’s summary, response, and calculation shown in the following tables:

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	150	69.8	69.8	69.8
Valid Female	65	30.2	30.2	100.0
Total	215	100.0	100.0	

Plainly male respondents were more in total for the reason that it is absurd to expect to depute and force female to offer some an ideal opportunity to fill the examiners.

Table 2: Ages of the Respondents:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Under 18 Years	19	8.8	8.8	8.8
18-25 Years	38	17.7	17.7	26.5
26-33 Years	60	27.9	27.9	54.4
Valid 34-41 Years	54	25.1	25.1	79.5
42-49 Years	28	13.0	13.0	92.6
50 and above	16	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	215	100.0	100.0	

These discoveries show that the most extreme respondents incorporate all around proficient and mature respondents who regularly consume various services in the area of Pakistan.

Table 3: Respondents of Educations:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
under Matric	17	7.9	7.9	7.9
Matric	19	8.8	8.8	16.7
Intermediate	17	7.9	7.9	24.7
Valid Graduate	31	14.4	14.4	39.1
Master	64	29.8	29.8	68.8
MPhil	67	31.2	31.2	100.0
Total	215	100.0	100.0	

Table: Profession of the Respondents:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Govt. Job	10	4.7	4.7	4.7
Private Job	90	41.9	41.9	46.5
Valid Un Employed	16	7.4	7.4	54.0
Scholar	99	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	215	100.0	100.0	

I chose respondents from various segments, approximately were as well scholars and private employ. It is a logical outcome such as without a job individuals are not in the budgetary situation just before select brands similarly as maximum, government job holders too did not have a preferred brand.

Reliability Analysis

As a result of the assessment, the information reliability investigation (Cronbach alpha unwavering quality) was run in SPSS to analyze the reliability of the tool used. Reliability analysis is the technique to check the level of dependability aftereffect of the estimation. Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) give details on the average of the Cronbach alpha consistency significance 0.70 saw great dependability. In calculation, Cronbach's Alpha is an exact proportion of dependability scales or analysis (Field et al. 2005). The valuation

of alpha must remain more conspicuous than 0.6 which an adequate range is (Van Zyl, Nerdecker, & Nel, 2000). The table below displays the reliability quality consideration when information is pilot tried.

Table 4: Reliability Analysis:

Factors	No. of item	Cronbach's Alpha
Service Quality	14	0.875
CRM	14	0.788
Perceived value	8	0.736
Customer satisfaction	6	0.794
Brand loyalty	7	0.871

According to the study of Hair et al, (2011), Cronbach’s alpha, if point 0.5 or less, then it is not acceptable. When Cronbach’s alpha is more than 0.5, or if point 0.6, then it is poor. If Cronbach’s alpha is at point 0.7 to 0.8, then it is good and, if Cronbach’s alpha is from 0.8 to 0.9, then it is excellent.

An ordinarily acknowledged instruction for significant inside strength utilizing Cronbach's alpha is by way of appearing, even though a bigger digit of highlights in the examination can raise the value of alpha and a model utilizing a lesser range can disrepute it, so this way had better be consumed with consideration. The assessment of Cronbach’s alpha of Service quality is .875, customer relationship management 0.788, and the assessment of Cronbach’s alpha of perceived value and customer satisfaction are 0.736 and 0.794 respectively. The value of Cronbach’s alpha of brand loyalty is 0.871 in the recent investigation.

Descriptive Statistics & Correlation Analysis

In this segment connection concerning the factors is examined in depth. Pearson correlation is registered on behalf of the chose examination factors. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) gives the degree of the connection among the factors. The aftereffect of correlation coefficients describes the level of interrelationships in the middle of the factors. Criticalness points are referenced with Asterisks, **=P<0.01, and *=p<0.05 individually. The mean estimation of services quality is 4.2520, standard deviation estimation is 0.4675, the estimate of the mean on behalf of customer relationship management is 4.1591 and standard deviation estimation is 0.7312, Perceived value estimation the value is 3.4369 and the standard deviation is 0.3284, mean estimation of brand loyalty 3.5180 and the standard deviation is 0.4671, considerably even though the mean estimation of customer satisfaction which goes about as an intermediary in the recent examination is 4.2721 and the standard deviation is 0.6187.

Table 6: Correlation Matrix:

	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5
SQ	4.2520	0.4675	1				
CRM	4.1591	0.7312	.587**	1			
PV	3.4369	0.3284	.341**	.309**	1		
CS	4.2721	0.6187	.323**	.419**	.378**	1	
BL	3.5180	0.4671	.426**	.339**	.323**	.219**	1

Number of N=215

** . Connection is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 4.6 indications implies, standard deviation, and the correspondence between the factors that are be there concentrate in this assessment and the estimation of correlation are describing the nature and level of the connection among the factors.

Analysis of Correlation:

Correlation analysis calculated the connection between the various factors. For assurance of connection in the mid of two factors, Pearson Product Moment is utilized. The outcomes of correlation investigation offer us the knowledge that all these factors are successfully correlated to each other.

At this point are the relationship ranges.

0.0 -- 0.4 (Relationship is Weak)

0.4 – 0.6 (Relationship is mediate)

0.6 – 0.8 (Relationship is High)

Over and above.8 (Multi-Collinearity)

For the most part, correlation analysis is lead to show the connection between the various factors. In this examination, the primary plan to direct connection investigation is to discover the connection among the factors. Determined qualities are between sure one +1 and the negative one - 1. At the point when the worth is nearer to +1, it demonstrates that the progressive connection is existent. If it is nearer to -1 at that point, a negative connection happens among the variables. The above table contains the results of correlation that exist between variables concentrated in the current report, for example; SQ, CRM, PV, CS, and BL.

The net result from the examination of correlation points out that there is a progressive and essential correlation between SQ and CS i.e. (.323**), CRM and CS (.419**), PV and CS (.378**), and CS and BL (.219**). There is additionally a progressive and critical relationship between SQ (intervene) and BL i.e. (0.426**), CRM and BL (0.309**), and PV and BL (.323**) which shows a weak relationship yet progressive and critical also. The estimations of all the variables progressively and critically mediating the connection with one another. We bring into being after examinations of connection between the factors that there is no multicollinearity problem, as a result, the factors are interconnected through one another.

Regression Analysis

In this research, relationship examination was directed to inspect the presence of alliances among various factors utilized in this analysis and there is a solid requirement to implement a regression analysis to gather credible proof of the support of one variable on another. Regression inquiry measures how considerably independent factors progressively and critical connection with the dependent variable. The regression techniques were used for hypothesis analysis. Linear regression analysis is utilized in the examinations to break down the hypothesis take on in the recent examination.

To respond to the analysis questions brought up in this analysis and report the investigation objective, seven assumptions were verified and the outcomes of the information are described in this segment. Regression analysis was shown by way of un-normalized measurements Beta (β), **R2**, and ΔR^2 are accounted for the assumption is acknowledged or disallowed on the source of p equally influence standards.

Table 7: Regression Analysis:

Predictor(s)	Customer Satisfaction			Brand Loyalty			
	B	R ²	ΔR^2	B	R ²	ΔR^2	Significance
Step-1							
SQ	0.211***						0.000
CRM	0.317***						0.001
PV	0.225***	0.445	0.448				0.000
Step-2							
CS				0.371***	0.475	0.479	0.000

Note: Number of sample size is 215 ***= P≤ 0.001, **= P≤ 0.01, *= P≤ 0.05

Outcomes from this examination of regression indicate that service quality has a huge & progressive connection with brand loyalty by way of the estimation of β are 0.211 at the level of impact and satisfy the prerequisites that level of significance less than or equal to 0.001, which is an agreeable scope of assumption. The value indicates that 0.211 units' modification is gained in the service quality due to a 1 unit variation in brand loyalty. This supports our study assumption H1 which was expressed SQ has a considerable impact on BL. The Association of CRM and BL in this table shown that **beta** is 0.317, level of significance is less than or equal to 0.001. This indicates that 0.317 unit adjustment is brought about in BL due to a 1 unit variation in CRM. The result has shown that there is H2 accepted. Discoveries of regression investigation show that PV has a progressive bond with BL by way of the worth of β is (0.225), level of significance is 0.001, and, which is accepted scope of assumption H3. It indicates that 0.225 units' modification is caused in BL by reason of 1 unit modification in PV. Consequences of the regression investigation indicated that CS mediates the connection in the intermediate of SQ and BL for instance the worth of β is 0.371 at the impact level at the esteem of level of significance less than or equal to 0.001, which is an adequate scope of hypotheses and H4 is accepted. Current progression, we decided that the estimate of **beta** is 0.371 which appearances a 37% variety in BL which conveys that the facilitating impact of CS gets 37 % variation in the model. Effects of the mediating impact of CS on SQ and BL proposed that CS intermediates the connection between Independent and dependent in this research. The values of regression investigation indicated that $\beta = .471$, level at the estimation of $p \leq 0.001$, which is an adequate scope of hypotheses. The result shows a 47% change in BL which communicates that the mediating influence of CS. H5 is accepted. Consequences of the intermediating impact of CS on CRM and BL proposed that CS facilitates the connection between CRM and BL. By way of the estimation, the value of β is 0.479 by the estimation of the level of significance is on 0.001, which is an adequate scope of hypotheses. In this progression, we decided that the estimation of $\beta = 0.479$ which displays a 47% change in BL which conveys that the intermediating influence of CS carries a 47 % variation in the model. Outcomes of the facilitating influence of CS on the PV and brand loyalty proposed that CS intermediates the link in the middle, H6 is accepted.

Discussion

On behalf of the recent examination, it has been shown by the outcomes that SQ, CRM, and PV have an influence on BL with the mediating part of CS. CS goes about as a facilitator between independent and dependent variables. Discoveries for this investigation demonstrate that there is a positive connection between these factors. This investigation additionally inspected that when customer satisfaction is used for intermediating the possibility of BL becomes greater in the service sector of Pakistan. Even though there are various studies showed on SQ, CRM, and PV and brand loyalty in earlier works using different hypotheses. The investigation of the planned hypothesized model has been focused on different areas. From the current writing and dependent on investigation targets for this examination, seven hypothesizes were created. Examination destinations were accomplished by analyzing this assumption.

The numerical investigation was run on together facts concluded SPSS and indication remarkable effects which are as stated that service quality has a positive impact on customer satisfaction. Service quality was seen as positively and altogether identified with customer satisfaction. This finding is pleasing with the example which was found in various western examinations, Lasser et al; (2001), Hussain, (2016). Similarly, according to the **H2** CRM has a positive effect on CS. Following the information examination, the hypothesis was accepted. The previous study of Kolis and Jirinova, (2013) also proved that CRM has positively connected with CS. **H3** Perceived value is also accepted as a cause of customer satisfaction. At that point when a customer got a boundless value of service, it will bring about high satisfaction. As it were, the superior the service quality, the upper the buyers' perceived value (Howat & Assaker, 2013). Numerical information proved PV has positively connected with CS. **H4** the fourth assumption the intermediating influence of CS among SQ and BL was tried. The discoveries have exposed that SQ has a hopeful and profound influence on BL as described in a table that proves our research assumption (H4). In earlier research, Hussain (2016) and Lim et al., (2006) demonstrate a huge influence of SQ on BL. In the past analysis, Osman and Sentosa (2013), Srivastava and Rai (2013) also used CS as a mediator between SQ and BL.

In the current study, **H5**, the hypothesis is accepted and discoveries and outcomes indicate that CS confidently and meaningfully mediates the connection between CRM and BL. As indicated through the reasonable context suggested by Faed (2010), CRM, improves the connection of consumers and challengers in a firm to raise the share of the business in the marketplace. According to, **H5**, the hypothesis is accepted and discoveries that customer satisfaction significantly facilitates the connection between Perceived Value and brand loyalty. The previous examination, (Hussain, 2016 & Ishaq et al, 2014). Likewise demonstrates the progressive intermediating effect of CS in the core of PV and BL. According to **H7**, The link between CS and BL has confidently huge. This assumption is acknowledged and outcomes indicated that CS clearly and expressively connected with the BL for the existing investigation. A previous study by Ishaq et al., (2014) also proved that CS positively connected with BL.

In this study, we examine the indirect connection of Service Quality and Brand Loyalty, Customer relationship management, and Brand Loyalty, and Perceived Value and Brand loyalty. We look at the connection of buyer satisfaction effects between these undertakings. Information gathered from the overall service consumer of different service areas of Pakistan and information were investigated through SPSS software to verify the link of these hypotheses. Our discovery exposes that brand loyalty is clearly and meaningfully affected by Service Quality, Customer relationship management, and Perceived Value with mediate Customer satisfaction between the associations of Service Quality, Customer relationship management, Perceived Value, and brand loyalty.

Implications for leaders and Manager:

When engaging managers, managers should concentrate on improving the quality of their services as these legitimate influences affect customer perception. With the innovation of the Internet, customers can deal directly with the business, which enables the company to acquire new consumers utilizing this innovative correspondence channel. In the service context, consumers focus on the quality components of the service, awareness, reliability, reliability, and security as well as reporting. Therefore, managers need to concentrate on the track record of quality services. In the service area, the company's service supplier met and communicated directly with clients. The impact of the company's image on brand loyalty will rise when clients are pleased with the services provided. Because the demographic data in this investigation show that the mainstream of respondents (27.9%) are between 26 and 33 years old, service organizations should support local events such as music, sports, or charities to gain a positive perception in people's minds. Managers should, therefore, concentrate on providing the customer with high-quality service and enabling them to appreciate the value of the services offered. This leads to the organization of brand value creation on the market.

Limitation and Future Direction:

The theoretical scheme of this survey has been recommended on a theoretical basis, the results come from the service sector and the sample in the study is 215. Upcoming researchers should, therefore, raise the total of samples used for further valid and authentic results. The upcoming scholar can able to furthermore rise the number of variables to achieve better participation, e.g. Analysis of the intermediating result of consumer satisfaction concerning brand loyalty for added variables such as the quality image perceived by customer service. Also, the brand image can be taken as a moderator. Future research is needed to discover other causes of brand loyalty. Further, to safeguard the generalize ability of our outcomes, the current examination depended on a cross-sectional example. In any case, the undertaking was directed to one single nation and ought to be stretched out to respondents from various nations to take into consideration cross-country approval. At last, the utilization of auxiliary conditions displaying in our examination recommends linearity of connection between the factors in our model. This suspicion could be considered as a constraint of our investigation and speaks to the potential for additional exploration areas. Upcoming research should study the other mediator between the link among service quality, perceived value, customer relationship management, and brand loyalty. As well, future research should also verify the effect of relationship value on brand loyalty, with the same or different mediator of customer satisfaction

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